

A Comparative Effect of Biochars with Different Quality, and Organic Manure on Plant Growth Rate in Beans Plant Cultivation

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ABSTRACT:

Balancing the need for increased food production and addressing environmental pollution associated with the use of inorganic fertilizers require sustainable farming practices. These practices include the use of eco-friendly soil enhancers such as biochar for agricultural purposes. In line with this, the study tends to compare the effect of biochars with different quality, and organic manure on the growth rate of cultivated beans plant. To assess the effect of the quality of different biochars on the rate of plant growth, beans seeds were planted in a combination of 150 g of soil, different biochars, and dried poultry manure in a ratio of 10:0.5:0.5. Three other control groups were established consisting of 150 g of soil mixed with 15 g of each of the different biochar samples only, 150 g of soil and 15 g of poultry manure only, and 165 g of soil only. The results showed that the plant grown in the soil in combination with biochar sample A (prepared at 350 °C and 40 min) and chicken manure, grew faster in height than the plants cultivated with other biochar samples and chicken manure. Also, the plant grown in the combination of soil, sample A and organic manure performed better in height by 35% compared to the plant in sample A and chicken manure alone and the beans planted in soil and biochar sample A alone. Hence, biochar produced at 350 °C and 40 min can act as an excellent improver in plant growth rate when used solely or in combination with other organic manure.

Keywords: Biochar quality, Organic manure, Plant growth rate, Beans cultivation.

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INTRODUCTION

In the face of rising food insecurity as a result of the growing world population, the issue of ensuring adequate plant growth has become crucial. Scientific advances of the twentieth century have led to the development of conventional farming practices and genetically modified plant breeds that have a faster growth rate and increased crop production. However, these improved breeds still need additional soil enhancers such as inorganic fertilizers and organic manure to achieve greater results. The Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO) reported that the global use of inorganic fertilizers

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increased by 46% from the period of 1990 to 2019 [1]. This massive use of fertilizers has led to an increase in global food production in the last decade [2].

Despite the advantages associated with the use of inorganic fertilizers such as providing readily water-soluble soil nutrients with rapid absorption and increased crop yields, the negative impact of polluting water bodies from agricultural run-offs, and nutrient imbalances are the main setbacks [3]. Consequently, the use of organic fertilizers from natural materials such as compost, biomass residues, and animal residues, has emerged as a better option to increase agricultural productivity while addressing the challenges of the use of inorganic fertilizers. They improve soil health, improve microbial activity and reduce environmental pollution [4]. One of the products from agricultural residues that have found its application as an excellent organic fertilizer is biochar.

Biochar is charcoal produced by the burning of biomass materials at temperatures ranging from 300-700 °C in the absence of oxygen or limited oxygen. It is used as a soil amendment for environmental and agricultural purposes. It is a porous solid, environmentally recalcitrant and has a lot of surface functional groups. The aforementioned properties, its specific surface area, and cation exchange capacity enable it to adsorb pollutants and retain water and nutrients in the soil. Its elemental composition shows it contains elements such as nitrogen, phosphorus, sodium, potassium, and silicon among others that act as a plant nutrient. Studies [5, 6] have shown that appropriate biochar amendment is effective in ameliorating soil physical, chemical, and biological properties, increasing crop productivity, and reducing the bioavailability of heavy metals and organic contaminants in soil.

However, the properties possessed by biochar are a function of the conditions used for pyrolysis. Some works [7, 8] have produced biochar at lower temperatures and varying times while some have produced it at higher temperatures [9, 10] for specific applications. The effectiveness of biochar application is a function of its properties. Although biochar produced at different conditions has been applied to improve plant growth, a comparative assessment of the combined effect of different biochars produced at different conditions, and organic manure on the rate of plant growth in a cultivated agricultural plant is limited. There is a need for increased knowledge on the effect of biochar with different qualities on the rate of plant growth. Consequently, this study aims to compare the effect of biochars with different quality, and organic manure on the growth rate of beans plant in a greenhouse experiment. Specifically, the study tends to:

- Investigate the potential of biochar to improve plant growth;
- Compare the performance of biochar with different properties on plant growth;
- Compare the combined effect of biochars with different properties and other soil amendments, such as organic fertilizer on plant growth.

Understanding how these factors influence biochar properties can help optimize its use in agriculture to enhance crop productivity and soil health.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The primary raw material used as organic fertilizers were different biochar samples from bean shafts prepared by pyrolysis by the research group at the Department of Chemical Engineering, Lagos State University Laboratory. The bean seeds planted were improved Nigerian breeds bought from a local market in Egbeda, Nigeria. The soil used in the experiment was collected from an agricultural field at the Lagos State University, Epe Campus. Dried chicken manure was collected as another type of organic manure from a farm settlement in Epe, Lagos.

Biochar Properties

The different samples of biochar (sample A-F) used as a type of organic manure had varying properties from the presence of hydrogen groups in the single bond region to different organic compounds in the double bond region and no compounds in the triple bond region. Just a sample of the biochar (sample B) had organic compounds in the fingerprint region (Table 1).

Table 1. Properties of Biochars Used as Organic Fertilizers

Biochar samples	A	B	C	D	E	F
Pyrolysis conditions	350 °C, 40 min	500 °C, 40 min	700 °C, 40 min	350 °C, 80 min	500 °C, 80 min	700 °C, 80 min
Properties						
Elements						
Carbon	68.24	71.54	62.14	69.10	60.08	72.00
Oxygen	10.30	10.30	20.00	7.20	20.25	9.30
Phosphorus	6.22	6.20	7.18	12.22	7.46	5.22
Magnesium	2.98	6.24	3.20	5.00		
Sodium	2.10	2.60		2.22	2.09	
Chlorine	2.02	2.00	0.09	0.50	1.22	0.31
Calcium	1.60	1.62	1.18	0.33	4.40	1.32
Nitrogen	0.50	1.43	3.22	3.20	0.45	5.20
Silicon	3.20	0.52	2.40	0.23	3.90	6.00
Iron					0.15	
Manganese			0.55			0.15
Copper	2.14					0.50
Organic compounds						
Hydroxyl groups	✓	✓	×	×	×	×
Oxygen-related functional groups	×	×	×	×	×	×
Ammonium/amino group	✓	✓	×	×	×	×
Unsaturated compounds/aromatic rings	✓	✓	×	×	×	×
Aliphatic compounds	✓	×	✓	×	×	×
Compounds with double bonds	×	✓	✓	✓	✓	×
Aldehydes	×	×	×	×	×	×
Compounds with triple bonds	×	×	×	×	×	×
Vinyl related compounds	×	×	×	×	×	×
Trans unsaturated vinyl compounds	×	×	×	×	×	×
-Orto and -Para aromatic compounds	×	✓	×	×	×	×
Porosity						
Average pore size (µm)	12.8	42.0	60.8	29.5	44.3	18.5
% Pore Area	27.4	40.0	39.3	15.8	25.1	9.7

Beans Plant Cultivation

To assess the combined effect of the different biochars and organic manure on the plant growth rate, six disposable cups, each weighing between 7.5 and 7.9 g, were filled with 150 g of contaminated soil, combined with 7.5 g of biochar and 7.5 g of poultry manure in the ratio 10:0.5:0.5. To assess the direct effect of the different biochars on the rate of plant growth, three control groups were established. The first control group consisted of 150 g of soil mixed with 15 g of each of the different biochar samples in a ratio of 10:1. The second control group included 150 g of soil and 15 g of poultry manure only, serving as a fertilizer treatment. The third control group consisted of 165 g of soil only. After preparing each sample, the soil was thoroughly mixed, and three bean seedlings were planted in each cup. The plant in each cup (Figure 1) was watered in the evenings daily with 8 ml of water each. To facilitate drainage and prevent waterlogging, a small hole was punctured at the bottom of each cup. The plants were placed in sunlight during the day and brought into the laboratory in the evening. Records of the daily growth of the plants were taken using a 30 cm measuring tape. The growth and development of the plants were monitored for four weeks.

Figure 1. Cultivated Beans Plant

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effect of Biochar Properties on Growth Rate

The results of the effect of biochar properties on the rate of the beans growth are presented in Figure 2. The results show that the plant grown with soil and biochar sample A, produced at 350 °C and 40 min, had faster growth in height than the plants cultivated with other biochar samples. The plant cultivated with biochar sample A had a 12% increase in height to plants planted with sample B, a 25% increase in height than plants planted with sample C, a 39%, increase in height to plants planted with sample D, 16%, increase in height than plants planted with sample E and 65% increase in height than plants planted with sample F. The plants grown with samples E and F performed the least in terms of height. The number of leaves on the beans plant with sample A was more than the leaves of other samples. This might be due to the large amount of organic compounds present in sample A compared to other biochar samples.

Figure 2. Effect of Different Biochars: G (sample A and soil), H (sample B and soil), I (sample C and soil), J (sample D and soil), K (sample E and soil), L (sample F and soil) on the Height (a) and Leaves (b) of Plants

The Combined Effect of Biochar Properties and Organic Manure on Growth Rate

The results of the combined effect of biochar properties and chicken manure on the rate of the beans growth are presented in Figure 3. The results show that the plant grown in the soil with the combination of biochar sample A and chicken manure had faster growth in height than the plants cultivated with other biochar samples and chicken manure. The plant cultivated with biochar sample A and chicken manure had a 37% increase in height to plants planted with sample B and chicken manure, a 12% increase in height than sample C and chicken manure, 45%, increase in height to sample D and chicken manure, 48%, increase in height than sample E and chicken manure and 47% increase in height than sample F and chicken manure. The plant grown with sample F performed the least in terms of height. The number of leaves on the beans plant was more than the plants of other samples. The plant with soil, sample A and organic manure performed better in height by 5.6% (Figure 3a) and had more leaves (Figure 3b) compared to the plant with sample A and soil alone (Figures 2a and 2b).

Figure 3. The Combined Effect of Different Biochars and Organic Manure on the Height (a) and Leaves (b) of Plants

Effect of Replacement of Biochar with Organic Manure on Growth Rate

To assess the effect of using chicken manual alone as a replacement to biochar, beans plant was planted as another control using soil and chicken manure. The results of the use of chicken manure on the rate of beans growth are presented in Figure 4. The results show that the plant grown with soil and chicken manure had slower growth in height (Figure 4a) and leaves (Figure 4b) than the plants cultivated with other biochar samples and chicken manure (Figure 3) and biochar samples alone (Figure 2). The plant with soil, sample A and organic manure performed better in height by 35% compared to the plant with sample A and chicken manure alone. The beans planted in soil and biochar sample A performed better in height by 31% than those planted in soil and chicken manure.

Figure 4. The Effect of Planting Replacing Biochar with Chicken Manure as a Fertilizer on the Height (a) and Leaves (b) of Plants

Effect of Soil Fertilizers on Growth Rate

To assess the importance of using soil fertilizers to aid plant growth, a control sample was planted without chicken manure and biochar and the effect was studied for 7 days. The results show that the rate of plant growth was slower when compared to planting with biochar alone as a soil enhancer or in combination with biochar and chicken manure (Figure 5, Table 2). However, there was no significant difference in the plant height when compared to planting with chicken manure alone.

Figure 5. Plant Height as a Function of Days of Beans Planted without Soil Fertilizers

Table 2. Number of Leaves of Plants as a Function of Days of Beans Planted without Soil Fertilizers

Day	0	1	2	3	4	5
	No of leaves					
Control (1)	0	0	*	2	2	2

Control (2)	0	*	2	2	2	2*
Day	6	7	8	9	10	
	No of leaves					
Control (1)	2*	5	5	5*	8	
Control (2)	2*	5	5	5*	8	

Note: *leaves plus sprout

Optimizing Biochar Properties and Poultry Manure for Plant Growth

- **Combined application of soil, biochar and chicken manure**

The combined effect of soil with biochar and poultry manure significantly boosted the rate of plant growth and the highest growth rates were achieved with biochar produced at 350 °C for 40 min (Sample A) and 500 °C for 40 min (Sample B). This highlights the joint impact of biochar and other organic fertilizers, suggesting that their combined application can enhance plant growth and overall productivity.

The enhancement in plant growth can be linked to biochar's ability to improve both soil fertility and structure. Biochar has been demonstrated to increase the cation exchange capacity (CEC) of soil, enhance its capacity to retain water and create an environment conducive to beneficial microorganisms [11]. The addition of organic fertilizers further augments nutrient availability, which is crucial for plant development.

- **Soil and biochar (control group)**

The result also reveals that applying biochar to the sole solely can positively influence plant growth rates. In particular, the biochar produced at 350 °C for 40 min (Sample G) and 350 °C for 80 min (Sample H) yielded the most substantial growth within the control group. This suggests that biochar can serve as an effective soil amendment, improving plant growth even without the addition of poultry manure.

The increase in plant growth is again attributed to biochar's role in enhancing soil fertility and structure. Its ability to elevate the improve moisture retention, and support beneficial microbial life plays a crucial role in promoting plant health.

- **Soil and poultry manure (control group)**

The results demonstrate that using soil and poultry manure can also lead to significant improvements in plant growth rates. Serving as a control group, the fertilizer application resulted in notably robust plant growth. This indicates that fertilizers can effectively enhance plant growth (but not as fast) even in the absence of biochar.

- **Comparison of treatment groups**

When comparing the various treatment groups, it is clear that the combination of soil with biochar and poultry manure resulted in the highest rates of plant growth. This justifies that these two amendments can have on enhancing plant productivity.

Additionally, the study shows that biochar produced at 350 °C for 40 min (Samples A) and 500 °C for 40 min (Sample B) was more effective in promoting plant growth than that produced at 350 °C for 80 min. This suggests that both the pyrolysis temperature and duration are critical factors influencing biochar's efficacy in enhancing plant growth.

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrated that pyrolysis conditions significantly impacted the quality of biochar and its effectiveness as a soil amendment. Biochar produced at 350 °C with a residence time of 40 min provided the best balance between stability and functional group retention, leading to improved plant growth with the highest plant height of 27 cm and 12 leaves on the stem of the plant after 29 days of cultivation when used in combination with chicken manure. In addition, the use of biochar

produced at 350 °C and 40 min alone as a soil enhancer also improved the plant growth rate with a plant height of 25 cm and 10 leaves after 29 days. Hence, biochar produced at 350 °C and 40 min can act as an excellent improver in plant growth rate when used in combination with poultry manure and can also be used solely in place of organic manure as a soil enhancer.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

No conflict of interest.

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